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Report on **Milestone 12**

Implementation plan SSHOC Switchboard and VCR Services

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Abstract:

The report contains a global workplan for SSHOC Task 3.6 with respect to SSHOC Switchboard and Virtual Collection Registry integration and extension.

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History

Version	Date	Reason	Revised by
1.0	30/09/2020	updated with latest state of affairs Switchboard use-cases and software development	Daan Broeder
2.0-0.3	30/12/2020	V2.0, V3.0 updated for internal purposes only	Daan Broeder
4.0	08/03/2021	updated with the latest information with regards to Switchboard and VCR development plans	Daan Broeder

1. Introduction

The milestone MS12 is described in the SSHOC GA as an “Implementation plan SSHOC Switchboard and VCR services”, verifiable by: “A flexible planning for the extension and integration of SSHOC Switchboard and VCR”.

The nature of the SSHOC Switchboard and the potential and interest of the SSHOC WP3 partners to generalize and apply it within the SSH is described in SSHOC MS9. This report is a follow-up of that document, describing activities in more detail where needed and proposing a general work plan for the implementation activities.

Plans for a SSHOC Virtual Collection Registry (VCR) have for now only been discussed in a limited fashion between the CLARIN ERIC and UGOE partners and not been subject to any structured interaction between all the SSHOC partners. Therefore, the current state of the implementation plan is that it covers the work on the SSHOC Switchboard, next steps will provide for the involvement of more partners and their respective interests and views for the SSHOC VCR work, expanding the initial requirements and ideas for VCR extensions and adaptations.

2. Description of the Milestone

2.1. Role of the Milestone

The basis of MS12 is the SSHOC MS9 report, that presents a number of important overviews based on the outcomes of discussions with the SSHOC WP3 partners for MS12:

- An overview of the Switchboard integration opportunities (SSH data catalogues);
- An overview of potentially useful services that can be integrated in the Switchboard and offer added value for SSH users working with SSH data-types;
- An overview of potential Switchboard extensions that increase its usefulness and/or are needed to work with new data-types;
- A number of templates filled in by the WP3 partners (and some outside of the Consortium) providing information about their potential contributions.

In MS12 we bring those overviews together in a way that enables choices for the work of the WP3 partners. While at the same time leaving a reasonable number of resources for work on the VCR.

At the moment of the initial Implementation plan being finalised, the team planned ahead for M13-M24. Additionally, more specific planning documents for the upcoming periods will be created along the way.

The number of resources available varies among the different partners, and some partners have considerable overlap in activities over the different WP3 tasks e.g. T3.4 (CNR, CLARIN), T3.5 (CNR, CLARIN, OEAW), T3.6 (CNR, CLARIN, OEAW). In discussions with T3.4, T3.5, T3.6 task leaders agreed to maximize the synergy of the work on those tasks.

TABLE 1 WP3 PARTNERS AND RESOURCES

Partner	PMs M1-M40	VCR work reserved	Comment
CLARIN ERIC	15 - 6	6 (tbd)	6PM for task coordination Switchboard operations
CNR	4+12	-	12 PMs in other WP3 tasks with Switchboard synergy
DAI	4	-	
EKUT	22	-	Main Switchboard development
OEAW	6	-	
UGOE	8	4 (tbd)	

The authors define a number of activity classes for the planning and indicate the partners that seem most suitable to be involved in such activities because of their expertise or overlap with other tasks.

Main tasks:

- (SD) development Switchboard: EKUT, CLARIN, CNR
- (VCRD) development VCR: CLARIN ERIC, UGOE
- (SBI) integration of Switchboard: all
- (VCRI) integration of VCR: all
- (SI) integration of existing services: all
- (SRB) building of new services.
- (C) Consultancy with respect to domain, data-types or service specifics.

Software development work (SD and SRB) is assumed to include creating specifications for specific (sub) parts of the work in discussion with the task leader and other stakeholders.

The pure Switchboard development work is done by EKUT and supported by the CLARIN ERIC especially with respect to operations for the Switchboard production version. This includes (1) extending the Switchboard with (experimental) functionality as described in SSHOC MS9 and in common specification document (to be made available in M13) and (2) some necessary auxiliary actions as, for example, better data-type recognition (e.g. TEI, Folia) etc.

Table 2 shows an overview of the Switchboard and Switchboard services development tasks, while the Switchboard actual integration and further activities are described in the appendices to this document. (Question marks indicate still to complete or verify information):

- Appendix A *Specification for the Switchboard development process*
- Appendix B *Switchboard integration tasks*
- Appendix C *Auxiliary tasks*
- Appendix D *Planning the SSHOC Virtual Collection Registry.*

TABLE 2 SWITCHBOARD AND SERVICES DEVELOPMENT AND INTEGRATION TASKS

	Name extension	Responsible	Estimated time/date	Comment	Status Sept 2020 - Q7	Status Feb2021 - Q9
SD0	Develop next version Switchboard API, allowing easy upgrades of the Switchboard UI	EKUT	Q5 (Jan-Mar 2020), 1PM	Related to SD1,2,3,5	done	

SD1	Lightweight Switchboard popup Including usage examples e.g., dictionaries Investigate the JS library vs Browser plugin approach	EKUT	Q6 (Apr-Jun 2020), 2PM	considered plug-in approach not viable.	partially done, DAI dictionary implemented in dev version, guidelines how-to implement it are available	Popup window refined, not integrated in any repository, test-page available, to be implemented in CLARIN version, integration in ARACHNE still under discussion
SD2	Support for Data Dowsing, rule-based extraction of data references from metadata/landing pages	EKUT, CNR	Q7 (Jun-Sept 2020), 1PM	Test repositories to still be identified	Delayed	Postponed until CLARIN Digital Object Gateway plans clarified
SD3	(Interactive) content visualization depending on data-type	EKUT, OEAW	Q7 (Jun-Sept 2020), 1PM	Needed for SD4, SD6	Delayed	Q10 together with iteration over container content, see also SEP11
SD4	Supporting (data) containers e.g. zip, tar	CLARIN /EKUT	Q7 (Jun-Sept 2020), 1PM	Where possible use external services	Delayed	Q10
SD5	Supporting data conversion	EKUT, CNR	Q8 (Oct-Dec 2020), 1PM	with T3.5 (FSD) discuss with 3.5, call existing conversion without UI services through Weblicht		analyse Interoperability Hub service list - link to existing services - offer new services from Weblicht
SD6	Actionable metadata, citation generation	EKUT, CNR	Q8 (Oct-Dec 2020), 1PM	with T3.4 (CRNS/Huma Num)	Possibly not relevant anymore	Task 3.4 was revised citation generation no longer relevant for SB. CMDI visualization via CMD explorer (done)
SRB1	Data Type recognition: TEI, Folia,	OEAW, CLARIN /EKUT	Q5 (Jan-Mar 2020), 2PM	with T3.5 (FSD)	TEI, Folia, JSON, done	

SRB1+	Including general type determining from header only avoiding large downloads if possible		1PM	Current version copies all the data to the SB storage		Depending on need from services that use large files, for now postponed
SI1	Ariadne Visual Media Service ¹	CNR, (tbd)	(tbd)	CNR to propose contribution ARACHNE would also be a prime target for integration	AVS ready, integrated in SB dev version	AVS ready, integrated in SB SSHOC version but problem with separate texture files, discuss with CNR for best solution specifying multiple files
SI2	Several data conversion services, eg. DDI, TEI, ...	CNR, CLARIN, OEAW		With 3.5 See SD5		
SI3	Dictionaries e.g. Perseus	EKUT, DAI	Q8 (Oct-Dec 2020)	ARACHNE depending on SD1 Only DAI dictionary available, Perseus not by lack of information, to ask Wolfgang		Wikipedia, DAI.vocab, DAI. gazetteer, GETTY, FCS integrated and available in SSHOC SB, done waiting for integration in ARACHNE ao.

¹ The Ariadne Visual Media Service (AVMS) is a service developed at the CNR/IST partner, although from a different group than the one that participates in the SSHOC project work. We hope to collaborate with the AVMS developers to facilitate integration of the AVMS in the Switchboard but cannot plan accurately.

SI4	GeoBrowser	UGOE	Q7 (Jun-Sept 2020)	Target catalogue: ARACHNE? discuss with DAI		tested on ARACHNE Gazetteer but Geobrowser is selective wrt KML data type and does not show proper error message. Discuss with UGOE the proper error handling
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2.2. Means of verification

The report and especially the tables 2 and 3 in this report, are the general work plan with respect to the Switchboard and VCR work in SSHOC WP3. The report also describes activities with respect to the Switchboard taking place outside the immediate context of the SSHOC project and plans for engagement and collaboration.

2.3. Explanation on delay in achieving the Milestone

The report for Milestone 9 was delayed two months to enable an extended and more thorough overview of the task 3.6 partners potential activities. This was enabled by a workshop organised by SSHOC Work Package 3 and the German CLARIAH-DE project on 12.-13 December 2019 in Göttingen. It was important to establish a common understanding of each other's goals and planned activities with respect to the Switchboard. The meeting in Göttingen was also instrumental to agree on common actions between CLARIN and UGOE partners with respect to the SSHOC VCR.

3. Conclusions and next steps

This report shows the current planning for the task 3.6 activities, including the workflow for follow-up planning and implementation.

Many listed individual Switchboard integration and extension tasks will still need to be further specified and discussed, and responsible partners for this have been allocated, and their context has been established.

For the work related to the SSHOC Virtual Collection Registry, we have established a collaboration between the CLARIN ERIC and UGOE partners. They will produce a first planning document in January 2020 and engage with the other partners to plan further extensions and uptake.

4. Appendix A – *Specification and Development Process*

All the tasks in Table 2 need to be worked out in more detail, but this is considered to be part of the specification/development work itself. To allow for a WP3 task 3.6 broad discussion and evaluation of the tasks, it was agreed that partners in the task should provide at least 2 pages per work topic. These should be discussed in the task meeting on the basis of aspects as:

- Feasibility & costs
- Applicability and suitability for the different stakeholder domains (consulting work).
- Impact for the project
- Maintainability and operations overhead

Outcome of those discussions might change the prioritization or cancelation of a specific task; however, cancelations should be exceptions.

Some tasks specified in the table are still very generally specified e.g., SRB1, SI2 with respect to the exact data-types and services to be involved. For these tasks an inventory should be specified in the next months in collaboration with WP3 task 3.5 “Interoperability Hub”, that is creating such inventories. Also, the foreseen collaboration with WP3 task 3.5 “Interoperability Hub” in SD6 should be discussed and noted in the task 3.5 workplan.

The 3.6 task leader will make sure the specification documents are made available and can be discussed at the 3.6 task meetings. Further details of the specification and development work can be maintained in publicly accessible source code repositories. The current CLARIN GitHub for the VCR and Switchboard development is thought sufficient for this. For new to develop services a different choice for hosting the source code can be made dependent on the partners involved.

5. Appendix B – Switchboard Integration Tasks

For the integration tasks we rely on partners that have control over the specific data catalogues or are involved in its conception. Consultancy support to be given by EKUT.

TABLE 3 SWITCHBOARD INTEGRATION TASKS

	Name integration	Responsible	Estimated time/planned date	Status & Comments
SBI1	ARCHE	OEAW	Q5 (Jan-Mar 2020)	done
SBI2	ARACHNE	DAI	Q6 (Apr-Jun 2020)	in progress
SBI3	DARIAH D repository	UGOE	Q5 (Jan-Mar 2020)	basic version done , to integrate popup version
SBI3	NAKALA	CNR	Q7 (Jun-Sept 2020)	HumaNum stated no resources available
SBI4	SSHOC DataVerse	CNR	tbd	With 5.2 (DANS) done in development version
SBI4	PARTHENOS VRE ²	CNR	completed, being tested (Feb 2021)	Improving current existing integration investigate SB pop-up version integration
SBI5	SND	EKUT	Q8 (Oct-Dec 2020)	With 3.5 (SND) depending on SI2, SD6 Did not find useful data and service combination, postpone until conversion services are available. e.g. DDI to CMDI

² The PARTHENOS VRE is a result from the PARTHENOS platform and maintained by the CNR/ISTI partner, although from a different group than participates in the SSHOC work. In collaboration with the PARTHENOS VRE maintainers, we will see how the current integration can be improved.

6. Appendix C – Auxiliary Tasks

There was the need to liaise with other SSHOC work packages and task within SSHOC and beyond, first with WP3 tasks 3.4 and 3.5 this already indicated in the tables of the work plan. Secondly there is a need to collaborate with WP7 working on the SSHOC Marketplace with regards to reuse or at least interoperability concerning the metadata description of services. A similar task is considered in promoting and working on the interoperability of the Switchboard with regards to EOSC/EOSC-hub.

TABLE 4 AUXILIARY TASKS AND PARTNERS

	Name	Responsible	Estimated time/planned date	Comment
Aux1	SSHOC Marketplace interoperability	OEAW	Q7 onward	guarantee interoperability To-do: investigate use of specialised dictionary for Marketplace resources
Aux2	Coordination with CLARIAH DE ³	EKUT	Q7 onward	Exploit synergy and guarantee interoperability - dienstenliste and SB service description synchronization e.g. desktop tools
Aux3	Switchboard positioning in EOSC / EOSChub	CLARIN	Q7 onward	made report to EOSChub by CLARIN

³ CLARIAH DE is a German national project in which the German DARIAH and CLARIN projects collaborate. One topic is the use of the CLARIN Language Resource Switchboard (Switchboard) by DARIAH.

7. Appendix D – Planning the SSHOC VCR

In the SSHOC GA description with respect to task 3.6 the creation of a SSHOC Virtual Collection Registry (VCR) is planned, based on generalizing and extending the current CLARIN VCR. The VCR permits users to create and register virtual collections which are sets of references to resources from different repositories together with some descriptive metadata describing the collection.

The CLARIN VCR is already a production quality service that is registered in the EOSC service catalogue. In SSHOC 3.6 we discuss with interested partners from the Social Sciences and Humanities how to make the VCR more suitable and appealing for the users of the partner infrastructures. In M13 it should become clear which VCR enhancements are thought useful for also the non-CLARIN partners and which partners are interested to work on this. For now, we have identified that both CLARIN and UGOE are interested to work on a SSHOC VCR. A short document will be provided Jan 2020 to inform the Social Sciences and Cultural Heritage WP3 partners and solicit requirements and involvement from their side.

After that full plan similar to what is now published for the Switchboard will be made available later in Q1 2020. All proposed VCR enhancements will then be discussed and prioritized in the 3.6 task meetings.

In the SSHOC GA there is one single VCR feature described: “A SSHOC virtual collection registry (VCR) integrated with the Switchboard supporting downloading into personal researcher workspace and sharing data selections with others”. Adding to this specifically mentioned feature, we include the current CLARIN list of planned and potential interesting enhancements which mentions:

- A simplified better internal data-model;
- The use of ORCID identifying authors/researchers;
- The possibility to enhance VCs after their initial creation, e.g., dynamic VCs.

First discussions with the UGOE partner, who did show an interest in VCR functionality (2019) took place discussing desirable extensions also from their viewpoint. Functionalities discussed were:

- Adding a VCR API following the RDA collection registry API⁴.

The CLARIN and UGOE partners will create a first requirements and planning document which will be used to engage with the other partners. Requirements from the other stakeholder infrastructures will be added also later in Q2 2020 (est.). There is a detailed list of VCR use-cases maintained by task 3.6 for internal discussion purposes.

⁴ RDA Alliance web: <https://www.rd-alliance.org/api-requirements-document> [accessed 16.03.2021]

TABLE 5 PLANNING THE SSHOC VCR TASKS

Task	Estimated time/planned date MS	Issue number/ links to VCR development track ⁵	Comment
VCR support DOIs	done	#69	done
save search results as VC	release 1/1.6.0 2-4-2021	#106 , #83 , #104	
support VC as search result basket cross repository (CESSDA use-case)	release 1/1.6.0 2-4-2021	#108 , #103 , #106	
support collaborative VC editing	release 1/1.6.0 2-4-2021	#81	
ERIHs use cases <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - resource creation; using VC as a basket combining search results - edit saved search results; user censors, annotates the search results - post-processing; compare search result query results over repositories 	release 1/1.6.0 2-4-2021	#104 , #103 , #69 , #81	No new requirements: For the download into personal workspace should investigate the use of PARTHENOS platform workspace. this is not included in the planned milestone
Support download consolidated VCR data into workspace / local disk	release 1/1.6.0 2-4-2021	#105	must have from SSHOC DoA
VCR as Research Object, Research Objects ⁶	release 2 no due date	#107	

⁵ VCR source code: <https://github.com/clarin-eric/VirtualCollectionRegistry> [accessed 16.03.2021]

⁶ Research Object website: <http://www.researchobject.org/> [accessed 16.03.2021]

Adding VCR API alignment with RDA collection registry	release 2 no due date		Still waiting on UGOE developer
Author identifiers (ORCID)	release 1/1.6.0 2-4-2021	#64	